

FIRM

FEHRL INFRASTRUCTURE RESEARCH MAGAZINE

On-Ramp to Innovation: Let's co-create together our Future Transport Infrastructure

FEHRL Infrastructure Research Meeting (FIRM 18)
20-21 March 2018, Assen, Drenthe

FEHRL

Overview of methodology for **RESIST** requirements.

In a vast road network comprising of continuously aging infrastructure, Managers and Operators are trying to increase the longevity of the network, meet safety standards and reduce costs. Nowadays, as IT tends to be more the backbone of every operations, this effort is extending to the cyber domain as well as to the physical infrastructures which need to be protected and be ready to effectively react to all kind of extreme natural events.

In order to achieve this, road infrastructure needs to be put under meticulous monitoring and analysis that will quickly, efficiently and accurately provide the right recommendations that will minimize any downtime to the operations of a road (or infrastructure of a road) and additionally ensure the safety of people using the infrastructure.

The **RESIST (RESilient transport InfraStructure to extreme events)** project analysed the most common damage detection techniques used right now across the industry, including non-destructive measurement equipment, vibration and ultrasonic sensors, cover meters as well as techniques such as photogrammetry, in order to achieve results of the same quality usefulness with the state of the art, and with the added advantage of reduction cost, time and increased safety of the inspection.

Nowadays more and more systems and operations of the road/transport managers are found outside the secure and protected environment of the operating companies. In addition, the increase in use of wireless devices and robotics agents in the structures monitoring adds another level of vulnerability against malicious attacks.

The RESIST project analysed the trends and challenges of the European road sector, state of the art in physical damage detection, prevention and response and discussion on mobility continuity in the cases of extreme events. Regarding cyber security, the research showed a number of cases of successful ITS-related cyber-attacks, convincingly providing that in today's world, cyber security is a valid and real concern. Therefore, it is important to accurately identify the major threats to the information system and plan actions

that can mitigate these threats. The Resist Project included the cyber security part starting with the real attacks that occurred and damaged from most serious cyber threats and RESIST cyber strategy. Therefore, the first draft of the system architecture was identified, which was followed by the user/functional requirements and scenarios for the test fields (pilots) that are planned later in the project. During the RESIST Workshop in Thessaloniki, two scenarios for each pilot were discussed:

The need for an in-depth knowledge and analysis of the requirements of the RESIST platform is an indisputable fact, especially due to the fact that RESIST platform combines several software and hardware technologies. In order to capture all the requirements of RESIST platform, including also the end-user requirements, a specific methodology has been followed.

The RESIST system requirements consist of the requirements that come from the end-users, the state-of-the-art analysis, and the RESIST DoA. The main focus is to extract all the end-user requirements that should be taken under consideration for the development of the RESIST platform. Figure xx presents the methodology to extract all the requirements (functional and non-functional).

The complete comprehensive list of the RESIST end-user requirements has been identified and it includes unique identifier per requirement, description, source, priority and range. Additionally, the list is being organized by thematic section that the requirement refers to. These requirements have been shared, discussed and agreed by the consortium and will be the driving material to be used to create the full specification set for RESIST system and ultimately create the technical frame of the project.

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LINKS

The RESIST project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 769066.

RESIST PARTNERS
